

Risk Factors for Glaucoma: A Hospital-based Case-control study**Md Mostaque Ahmed¹, Gitanjan Sarma², Mustaque Ahmed³, Monmohan Borah⁴**¹Demonstrator, Department of Community Medicine, Fakhruddin Ali Ahmed Medical College & Hospital, Barpeta²Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Fakhruddin Ali Ahmed Medical College & Hospital, Barpeta³Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Fakhruddin Ali Ahmed Medical College & Hospital, Barpeta⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Fakhruddin Ali Ahmed Medical College & Hospital, Barpeta

Received: 25-07-2024 / Revised: 23-08-2024 / Accepted: 26-09-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Md Mostaque Ahmed

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Glaucoma is a diverse group of eye diseases with a multifactorial etiology characterized by an acquired loss of retinal ganglion cells, progressive optic neuropathy with morphological abnormalities in optic nerve head, and visual field defect, in which raised intraocular pressure is a major and one of the modifiable risk factor and other risk factors includes age, gender, race, family history, systemic diseases, sociodemographic profile, etc. Glaucoma is a major public health problem, causing visual impairment which hampers day-to-day work.

Aims & Objective: 1. To study various risk factors For Glaucoma among patients attending OPD/IPD of RIO, GMCH. 2. To assess various socio-demographic, modifiable lifestyle-associated factors and other ocular diseases related to Glaucoma.

Materials and Methods: In this hospital-based case-control study, considering $p=10\%$, the sample size was calculated to be 570. Out of which 285 Cases and 285 Controls were selected from OPD/IPD of RIO, GMCH in a ratio of 1:1 after adjusting for age and sex. Verbal/written consent was taken followed by a detailed history was documented through a standardized predesigned and pretested proforma.

Results: All the data were analyzed and statistical significance was determined using SPSS software. A high prevalence of glaucoma was seen among males and most of the glaucoma cases belong to age 50-59 years. Statistically, a significant association was seen between age and Glaucoma but an insignificant association was seen with Gender. A high level of IOP (OR: 96.08, CI: 40.565-123.10 p-value: <0.0001), history of smoking (OR:1.515, CI:1.086- 2.113, p-Value-0.0181), history of alcohol use (OR:1.514, CI:1.072-2.139, p-Value:0.0230), history of use of steroid (OR:1.604, CI:1.123- 2.291, p-Value:0.0118), History of Myopia (OR:1.711, CI:1.228- 2.385, p-Value:0.0019), History of Diabetes Mellitus (OR:1.472, CI:1.048-2.066, p-Value:0.0315), history of Hypertension (OR:1.463, CI:1.051-2.034, p-Value:0.0294) showed statistically Significant association with Glaucoma. Whereas, other factors failed to show statistically significant association with Glaucoma.

Conclusion: In this study, various factors like smoking, alcohol use, and steroid use, high BP, high blood sugar, and some ocular factors (high IOP, Myopia) were found to be related to risk for Glaucoma. The mechanisms by which these factors lead to an increased risk of Glaucoma are still poorly understood, further study is needed to understand the significance of these as well as other factors as a risk for developing Glaucoma.

Keywords: Glaucoma, Risk factors, Hospital-based case-control study.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Glaucoma is a diverse group of eye diseases with a multifactorial etiology characterized by an acquired loss of retinal ganglion cells, progressive optic neuropathy with morphological abnormalities in optic nerve head, and visual field defect, in which raised intraocular pressure is a major and one of the modifiable risk factors [1] Although our modern under-

standing of glaucoma dates back only to the mid-19th century, this group of disorders was recognized by the Greeks as early as 400 BC. In Hippocratic writings, it appears as "Glaucois," about bluish-green hue of the affected eye. This term, however, was also applied to a larger group of blinding conditions that included cataracts. It was

not until 19th century that glaucoma was recognized as a distinct group of ocular disorders [2]. Glaucoma is a major public health problem, causing visual impairment which hampers day-to-day work [3] and Glaucoma is considered a lifelong disease and is a leading cause of irreversible but preventable blindness. The risk factors for Glaucoma are not only surrounded by the boundary of an eye but much more beyond the eye. The risk factors include age and frailty, gender, myopia, genetics, family history, smoking, race, systemic hypotension and hypertension, vasospasm, use of systemic or topical steroids, migraine, obstructive sleep apnea syndrome, and most significantly, increased IOP, etc. [2] The case detection rates must be increased by increasing awareness about glaucoma, thereby reducing blindness due to glaucoma. Early detection of glaucoma through "Opportunistic case detection" by performing a comprehensive eye examination at all levels and all available instances, and appropriate referral or initiating treatment as early as possible will help to improve the patient's quality of life [4].

As per WHO, there are approximately 76 million peoples in the globe who has been suffering from any form of Glaucoma [5]. This number is estimated to reach 111.8 million by 2040 [5] POAG and PACG are the most prevalent ones, being POAG at the top. Out of those 76 million people, 7.7 million develop moderate or severe visual impairment & 4.5 million blindness due to unaddressed Glaucoma [6]. In India, glaucoma is leading cause of irreversible blindness after cataract with at least 12 million people affected and nearly 1.2 million people blind from the disease. More than 90 percent of cases of glaucoma remain undiagnosed in the community [8]. It has been reported that glaucoma affects the quality of life to a greater degree in India than in the west [7]. Population-based studies suggest that more than 90% of glaucoma cases in the country remain undiagnosed. This contrasts with 40-60% rates of undiagnosed disease in more developed countries [9-13]. Glaucoma, although more commonly affects older adults above 40 years, it can occur in all age groups and all strata of society making it a major public health problem with significant health and economic consequences. Nearly 1/5 of the population affected by glaucoma become blind in one or both eyes [14].

In most of the condition glaucoma remain undiagnosed because of Unawareness & missed diagnosis at health-care centers. So, by changing our lifestyle as well as by improving the standard of ophthalmic examination through gonioscopy and optic disc evaluation we can reduce the incidence of glaucoma to a huge extent.

The classical characteristics of glaucoma's are [15]

1. Abnormality of anterior portion of the eye that

results in increased IOP

2. Loss of retinal ganglion cells in a distribution that suggests injury occurred at optic nerve head (ONH)
3. Nerve fiber layer loss which corresponds to pattern of visual field loss.

According to the literature, about 60 types of glaucoma are known, however, most common are POAG and PACG.

The prevalence of various types of glaucoma including the major ones (POAG & PACG) is showing an upward trend in our country and for several reasons, this trend is likely to be increased in this part (Assam) of India also. Due to limited previous reports on this subject and the raising trend of various types of glaucoma incidence in Assam along with other North-East states, remain undiagnosed. So, an analysis of the magnitude of this problem in patients attending tertiary care Centre like the Regional Institute of Ophthalmology (RIO), GMCH, Gauhati, would provide us with important information regarding the risk factors for glaucoma and its disease process and investigate various risk factors for glaucoma in this part of Northeastern India.

Material and Methods

This was a hospital-based, case-control (1:1 ratio) study conducted in RIO, GMCH, and Guwahati from August, 2021 to July, 2022. Both cases and controls were selected from OPD/IPD of RIO during study period after they gave their consent.

Cases

Only Diagnosed Glaucoma patients (as per diagnostic protocol), who came to OPD/IPD of RIO, GMCH during study period except the following-

1. Patients refusing to participate in the study
2. Patients diagnosed/morbid with different terminal ophthalmological problems other than Glaucoma
3. Other Terminally ill (cancer, bedridden, etc.) patients & those who unable to respond

Psychologically deteriorated patient with Glaucoma (due to lack of appropriate cooperation)

Controls

Patients attending OPD/IPD of RIO, GMCH who after proper examination and investigations (by an ophthalmologist) were diagnosed with other ocular diseases except Glaucoma excluding -

1. Patients refusing to participate in the study
2. Both unilateral as well as bilateral blind patients
3. Terminally ill patients

Consent was (verbal/written) taken from both Cases and Controls.

Sample Size

In view of multiple risk factors being studied, to give an 80% power in a two-sided test with 5% alpha error for any factor whose exposure is assumed to be 40% among controls and assuming the associated odd ratios (OR) to be 2.0, total sample size was calculated to be 570. Thus, sample size of cases and control was 285 each, in a ratio of 1:1.

Data Collection

During the study period from August 2021 to July 2022, a total number of 2100 patients with Glaucoma were enrolled, out of which 1200 cases were diagnosed with POAG, and rest were with other types of Glaucoma.

All patients were identified as cases who met inclusion criteria for the study till the required sample

size was achieved.

After taking informed consent, data regarding the various risk factors were collected from both cases and controls separately and were filled up in a pre-designed, pretested interview schedule. Each of the cases and controls was interviewed face-to-face in the OPD/ IPD or other room of the OPD/IPD area (according to the convenience of the patient) in absence of any other family members or attendants. The interview was taken either in English, Hindi, or in the local language (Assamese) according to the level of their understanding. This face-to-face interview was done only after completion of general & Ophthalmological examination by an Ophthalmologist.

Results

Table 1: Distribution of cases as per Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	210	73.7
Female	75	26.3
Total	285	100

Table 2: Distribution of cases as per Age

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage
40-49	38	13.4
50-59	76	26.6
60-69	65	22.8
70-79	59	20.7
80-89	46	16.2
>90	1	0.3
Total	285	100

Table 3: Distribution of Cases according to Family History

Family History	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	55	19.3
No/Don't Know	230	80.7
Total	285	100

Table 4: Relationship between Cases and Controls according to their Age

Age Group	Cases	Controls	Total	Chi-Square	p-value
40-49	38 (13.4%)	74 (26%)	112 (19.7%)	22.363	0.0336
50-59	76 (26.6%)	49 (17.1%)	125 (22%)		
60-69	65 (22.8%)	71 (25%)	136 (23.8%)		
70-79	59 (20.7%)	46 (16.1%)	105 (18.5%)		
80-89	46 (16.2%)	40 (14.0%)	86 (15%)		
>90	1 (0.3%)	5 (1.8%)	6 (1%)		
Total	285 (100%)	285 (100%)	570 (100%)		

Rural	111 (38.9%)	145 (50.9%)	256 (44.9%)		
Urban	174 (61.1%)	140 (49.1%)	314 (55.1%)		
Total	285 (100%)	285 (100%)	570 (100%)		

Table 5: Relationship of cases and controls according to their Gender

Gender	Cases	Controls	Total	Chi-Square	p-value
Male	210 (73.7%)	195 (68.4%)	405 (71%)	1.672	0.1960
Female	75 (26.3%)	90 (31.6%)	165 (29%)		
Total	285 (100%)	285 (100%)	570 (100%)		

Table 6: Relationship of cases and controls according to IOP Value

IOP Value	Cases	Controls	Total	Chi- Square	p-value	Odds Ratio CI
>21mmHg	240 (84%)	20 (8%)	260 (46%)	339.18	<0.0001	96.08 (40.565- 123.10)
≤21mmHg	45 (16%)	265 (92%)	310 (54%)			
Total	285 (100%)	285 (100%)	570 (100%)			

Table 7: Relationship of cases and controls according to family history

Family H/O Glaucoma	Cases	controls	Total	Chi-Square	p- value
Yes	55 (19.3%)	44 (15.4%)	99 (17.4%)	1.222	0.2689
No/Don't knows	230 (80.7%)	241 (84.6%)	471 (82.6%)		
Total	285 (100%)	285 (100%)	570 (100%)		

Table 8: Relationship of cases and controls according to history of smoking

H/O smoking	cases	controls	Total	Chi- Square	p-value	Odds Ratio (CI)
Yes	139(48.8%)	110(38.6%)	249(43.7%)	5.591	0.0181	1.515 (1.086-2.113)
No	146 (51.2%)	175 (61.4%)	321 (56.3%)			
Total	285 (100%)	285 (100%)	570 (100%)			

Table 9: Relationship of cases and controls according to history of alcohol use

H/O Alcohol use	cases	controls	Total	Chi- Square	p-value	Odds Ratio (CI)
Yes	115 (40%)	88 (30%)	203	5.172	0.0230	1.514 (1.072-2.139)
No	170 (60%)	197 (70%)	367			
Total	285 (100%)	285 (100%)	570 (100%)			

Table 10: Relationship of cases and controls according to history of use of steroid

H/O Steroid use	Cases	controls	Total	Chi- Square	P-value	Odds ratio (CI)
Yes	105 (36%)	76 (26%)	181 (32%)	6.347	0.0118	1.604 (1.123- 2.291)
No	180 (64%)	209 (74%)	389 (68%)			
Total	285 (100%)	285 (100%)	570 (100%)			

Table 11: Relationship of cases and controls according to history of tobacco use

H/O of tobacco use	cases	controls	Total	Chi- Square	p-value
Yes	168 (58.9%)	156 (54.7%)	324 (56.9%)	0.8653	0.3523
No	117 (41.1%)	129 (45.3%)	246 (43.1%)		
Total	285 (100%)	285 (100%)	570 (100%)		

Table 12: Relationship of cases and controls according to History of Myopia

History of Myopia	Cases	Controls	Total	Chi-Square	p-value	Odds Ratio (CI)
Present	156 (54.7%)	118 (45.2%)	274 (48%)	9.621	0.0019	1.711 (1.228- 2.385)
Absent	129 (45.3%)	167 (54.8%)	296 (52%)			
Total	285 (100%)	285 (100%)	570 (100%)			

Table 13: Relationship of cases and controls according to History of Eye Surgery

H/O Eye Surgery	Cases	Controls	Total	Chi-Square	p-value
Yes	40 (14.0%)	35 (12.2%)	75 (13.1%)	0.2457	0.6202
No	245 (86.0%)	250 (87.8%)	495 (86.9%)		
Total	285 (100%)	285 (100%)	570 (100%)		

Table 14: Relationship of cases and controls according to Types of Diabetes Mellitus

Type of DM	Cases	Controls	Total	Chi-Square	p-value
Type-1	16 (13%)	11 (11.3%)	27 (12.2%)	0.02803	0.8670
Total	123 (100%)	97 (100%)	220 (100%)		

Table 15: Relationship of cases and controls according to history of Hypertension

H/O Hypertension	Cases	Controls	Total	Chi-Square	p-value	Odds Ratio(CI)
	n%	n%	n%	4.745	0.0294	1.463 (1.051- 2.034)
Present	158 (55.4%)	131 (46%)	289 (51%)			
Absent	127 (44.6%)	154 (54.0%)	281 (49%)			
Total	285 (100%)	285 (100%)	570 (100%)			

Table 16: Relationship of cases and controls according to history of Thyroid disorder

H/O	Cases	Controls	Total	Ch-Square	p-value
Thyroid Disorder				0.1175	0.7318
Yes	110 (38.6%)	115 (40.4%)	225 (39.5%)		
No	175 (61.4%)	170 (59.6%)	345 (60.5%)		
Total	285 (100%)	285 (100%)	570 (100%)		

Table 17: Relationship of cases and controls according to Types of Thyroid disorder

Types of Thyroid disorder	Cases	Controls	Total	Chi-Square	p-value
Hyperthyroidism	52 (47.2%)	55 (47.9%)	107	0.006903	0.9338
Hypothyroidism	58 (52.8%)	60 (52.1%)	118		
Total	110 (100%)	115 (100%)	225 (100%)		

Table 18: Relationship of cases and controls according to history of Migraine Headaches

H/O	Cases	Controls	Total	Chi-Square	p-value
Migraine Headaches				0.2672	0.6052
Present	56 (19.6%)	62 (21.8%)	118 (20.7%)		
Absent	229 (80.4%)	223 (78.2%)	452 (79.3%)		
Total	285 (100%)	285 (100%)	570 (100%)		

Table 19: Relationship of cases and controls according to history of Vasospasm related disorders

H/O	Cases	Controls	Total	Chi-Square	p-value
Vasospasm-related disorders				0.7327	0.1167
Present	44 (15.4%)	48 (16.8%)	92 (16.1%)		
Absent	241 (84.6%)	237 (83.2%)	478 (83.9%)		
Total	285 (100%)	285 (100%)	570 (100%)		

Table 20: Relationship of cases and controls according to history Obstructive sleep apnoea

H/O	Cases	Controls	Total	Chi-Square	p-value
Obstructive sleep apnoea				0.2256	0.6348
Present	39 (13.6%)	44 (15.4%)	83 (14.5%)		
Absent	246 (86.4%)	241 (84.6%)	487 (85.5%)		
Total	285 (100%)	285 (100%)	570 (100%)		

Glaucoma is a heterogeneous group of diseases that primarily affects peripheral vision. In some others, it is regarded as a heterogeneous neuropathy that causes irreversible blindness. Worldwide, it is the second most common cause of blindness after cataracts. The Male to Female Ratio in India & World is 1.06:1 & 1.36:1 respectively. [16-19] in our study, prevalence of Glaucoma in Males is more than the females. Which is supported by R George et al. [16], VV KapetanakisIt et al. [17], YC Tham et al. [18], and K Allison et al. [19].

Our study, showed a statistically significant association between Glaucoma and Gender as a risk factor. This is supported by Framingham Eye Study [20], Rotterdam Study [21], Barbados Eye Study [22], etc.

In our study, a higher Prevalence of Glaucoma is seen in age group 50-59 years. This result is same with MW Tuck et al. [23] except for age group 80-89 years.

In our study, increasing age found to be a risk for Glaucoma. This is supported by AR Rudnicka et al. [24], Medical Advisory Secretariat, UK [25], PJ Foster et al. [26], Baltimore Eye Study [27], Barbados Eye Study [28], G Guedes et al. [29], Antonio Greco et al. [30], etc.

Our study shows a statistically significant association between high IOP and Glaucoma (P-value: <0.0001). This is supported by almost all the studies like Anne L Coleman et al. [31], YC Tham et al. [18], Los Angeles Latino Eye Study [24], The Rotterdam Study [21], Blue Mountains Eye Study [22], etc. Infect, IOP is one of the well-established modifiable risk factors for Glaucoma. In our study there is a statistically insignificant association between family history & Glaucoma (P-value: 0.2689). This is in contrast with A Le et al. [26], Tielsch et al. [15] {family history of glaucoma was higher in siblings (odds ratio: 3.69) than in parents (OR: 2.17) or children (OR:1.12)}

In our study statistically insignificant association was seen between smoking and Glaucoma (P-value: 0.2689). This is supported by Wise et al. [32] (P-value-0.28)

In our study, no association was seen between history of obstructive sleep apnea and Glaucoma (P-value: 0.6348). This result is supported by CA Girkin et al.

[33] (p-value = 0.18, OR = 1.80, 95% CI 0.76-4.23). Timothy V Roberts et al. [34], Tejaswini Prashant Khandgave et al. [35] found no association. In contrast, Lin et al. [36] 2013, Chen et al. [37] 2014, found association.

In our study an insignificant association was seen between history of migraine/ vasospastic disorders and Glaucoma (p-value: 0.6052). This result is supported by A Pradalier et al. [38] where they stated that migraine was not associated with any form of Glaucoma (P-value: 0.07). Landers et al. [39], Lin et al. [36] also found same result. Whereas, C Cursiefen et al. [40], showed a significant association for, normal tension Glaucoma P-value was <0.05 & high-tension Glaucoma P-value was <0.01, Blue Mountains Eye study [41], also found positive association. In our study, an insignificant association was seen between history of thyroid disorders and Glaucoma (P-value: 0.7318). This is supported by P Karadimas et al. [42], (P-value: 0.3, R: -0.08), Stephen P Motsko et al. [43]. In contrast KD Smith et al. [44], Boles Carenini B et al. [45], etc. found an association (P-value: 0.02,0.001,0.011 respectively)

In our study, there is a significant association between Hypertension & Glaucoma (P-value: 0.0294) This is supported by various studies like JMS Langman et al. [46] Blue Mountains Eye Study etc. In contrast, Amit K Deb et al. [47], Lingam Vijaya et al. [48] found contra indicatory interpretation.

In our study, a statistically significant association was seen between diabetes mellitus and Glaucoma

(P-value: 0.0315). Which is supported by Los Angeles Latino Eye Study, Vikas Chopra, et al. [49], P Mitchell et al. [50], Louis R Pasquale et al. [51], Beaver Dam Eye Study [52] (P-value: 0.004). In contrast to our study, Ellis et al. 2000 [53] (RR=1.57, 95% CI 0.99-2.48), De Voogd et al. 2006 [54] (RR=0.65, 95% CI 0.25-1.64), Vijaya et al. 2014 [55] (OR=1.07, 95% CI 0.62-1.82) found insignificant association.

In our study, a statistically significant association was seen between history of myopia and Glaucoma (P-value: 0.0019). Which is supported by Casson et al. [56], Ramakrishnan et al. [57], Xu et al. [58]. In contrast Wong et al. [59], Garudadri et al. [60], Perera et al. [61] found insignificant association.

In our study a statistically significant association is seen between history of smoking and Glaucoma (P-value: 0.0181), which is supported by Mónica Pérez- de-Arcelus et al. [62], Fan et al. [63], Renard et al. [64] In contrast, Kang et al. [65], Kaimbo et al. [66], Wang et al. [67], found insignificant association.

In our study, statistically significant association is seen between history of steroid use and Glaucoma (P-value: 0.01), which is supported P Mitchell et al. [68], E Garbe et al. [69], Opatowsky et al. [70], Shroff et al. [71]. In contrast, Chang et al. [72], Alsaadi et al. [73] found insignificant association.

In our study a statistically significant association between alcohol use and Glaucoma. (p-value: 0.0230). which is supported by Wise et al. [74], A meta- analysis by V Kelsey et al. [75], Framingham Eye Study [20] (P-value:<0.01) in contrast Leske et al. [28], Kang et al. [65] found insignificant association.

Conclusion

In our study various risk factors are significantly associated with Glaucoma like High IOP, Myopia, Non-Modifiable factors like increasing age & marital status, Systemic diseases like Hypertension & Diabetes Mellitus and several modifiable risk factors like smoking, alcohol use, and steroid use etc. further study is needed in this domain to establish risk factors and to take proper steps to reduce it.

Ethical Clearance: Obtained from IEC, GMCH, Guwahati

References

- Dada T, Ichhpujan P, Lingam V, Ramaswamik, Kaushiks, Vyas P, Sarma P. Guidelines for medical management of primary open angle glaucoma. All India ophthalmological society 2011;p6
- Shields textbook of glaucoma, 6th edition
- Palimkar, A., Khandekar, R., & Venkataraman, V. (2008). Prevalence and distribution of glaucoma in central India (Glaucoma Survey 2001). Indian journal of ophthalmology, 56(1), 57–62. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0301-4738.37597>
- Tatham, A. J., Weinreb, R. N., & Medeiros, F. A. (2014). Strategies for improving early detection of glaucoma: the combined structure-function index. Clinical ophthalmology (Auckland, N.Z.), 8, 611–621. <https://doi.org/10.2147/OPTH.S44586>
- Allison, K., Patel, D., & Alabi, O. (2020). Epidemiology of Glaucoma: The Past, Present, and Predictions for the Future. Cureus, 12(11), e11686. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.11686>
- Sheybani, A., Scott, R., Samuelson, T. W., Kahook, M. Y., Bettis, D. I., Ahmed, I., Stephens, J. D., Kent, D., Ferguson, T. J., & Herndon, L. W. (2020). Open-Angle Glaucoma: Burden of Illness, Current Therapies, and the Management of Nocturnal IOP Variation. Ophthalmology and therapy, 9(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40123-019-00222-z> Bibliography Page 187
- Dr. Jose. Community health J 2008; 21(65) S103-S104 <https://www.nhp.gov.in/disease/eye-ear/glaucoma>
- Dandona L, Dandona R, Mandal P, Srinivas M, John RK, McCarty CA, et al.—Angle-closure glaucoma in an urban population in southern India: The Andhra Pradesh eye disease study. Ophthalmology 2000; 107:1710-6
- Dandona L, Dandona R, Srinivas M, Mandal P, John RK, McCarty CA, et al. —Open-angle glaucoma in an urban population in southern India: The Andhra Pradesh eye disease study. Ophthalmology 2000;107:1702-9
- Vijaya L, George R, Arvind H, Baskaran M, Raju P, Ramesh SV, et al. Prevalence and cause of blindness in the rural population of Chennai Glaucoma study.
- Ramakrishnan R, Nirmalan PK, Krishnadas R, Thulasiraj RD, Tielsch JM, Katz J, et al. —Glaucoma in a rural population of southern India: The Aravind Comprehensive Eye Survey. Ophthalmology 2003; 110:1484-90.
- www.npeb.nic.in, National programme for control of blindness(NPCB), Director General of Health and Family Welfare, Govt of India
- Dr Manish pandey, Dr Ronnie Jacob George, Dr Lingam Vijaya. Chapter —Glaucoma in India. Glaucoma Diagnosis And Management Pathways, page:3
- Paul F. Palmberg, Joney L Wiggs: mechanism of glaucoma, 1423, Vol 2. Ophthalmology: Yanoff, Duker
- George R, Ve RS, Vijaya L. Glaucoma in India: estimated burden of disease. J Glaucoma. 2010 Aug; 19(6):391-7. Doi: 10.1097/IJG.0b013e3181c4ac5b. PMID: 20711029.
- Kapetanakis VV, Chan MP, Foster PJ, Cook

- DG, Owen CG, Rudnicka AR: Global variations and time trends in the prevalence of primary open angle glaucoma (POAG): a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Br J Ophthalmol*. 2016, 100:86-93. 10.1136/bjophthalmol-2015-307223 BIBLIOGRAPHY Page 2 21
17. Tham YC, Li X, Wong TY, Quigley HA, Aung T, Cheng CY: Global prevalence of glaucoma and projections of glaucoma burden through 2040: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Ophthalmology*. 2014, 121:208120-90. 10.1016/j.ophtha.2014.05.013
 18. Allison K, Patel D, Alabi O. Epidemiology of Glaucoma: The Past, Present, and Predictions for the Future. *Cureus*. 2020 Nov 24; 12(11):e11686. Doi: 10.7759/cureus.11686. PMID: 33391921; PMCID: PMC7769798.
 19. Leibowitz HM, Krueger DE, Mauser LR. The Framingham Eye Study monograph: An ophthalmological and epidemiological study of cataract, glaucoma, diabetic retinopathy, macular degeneration, and visual acuity in a general population of 2631 adults, 1973–1975. *Surv Ophthalmol*. 1980 May Jun; 24(Suppl):335–610. [PubMed: 7444756]
 20. Dielemans I, Vingerling JR, Wolfs RC. The prevalence of primary open-angle glaucoma in a population-based study in The Netherlands. The Rotterdam Study. *Ophthalmology*. 1994 Nov; 101(11):1851–1855. [PubMed: 7800368]
 21. Leske MC, Wu SY, Hennis A, Honkanen R, Nemesure B. Risk factors for incident open-angle glaucoma: the Barbados Eye Studies. *Ophthalmology* 2008; 115: 85–93.
 22. Tuck MW, Crick RP. The age distribution of primary open-angle glaucoma. *Ophthalmic Epidemiol*. 1998 Dec; 5(4):173-83. Doi: 10.1076/oep.5.4.173.4192.
 23. Erratum in: *Ophthalmic Epidemiol* 1999 Mar; 6(1):84. PMID: 9894803.
 24. Rudnicka AR, Mt-Isa S, Owen CG, Cook DG, Ashby D. Variations in primary open-angle glaucoma prevalence by age, gender, and race: a Bayesian metaanalysis. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci*. 2006 Oct; 47(10):4254-61. Doi: 10.1167/iovs.06-0299. PMID: 17003413.
 25. Medical Advisory Secretariat. Routine eye examinations for persons 20-64 years of age: an evidence-based analysis. *Ont Health Technol Assess Ser*. 2006; 6(15):1-81. Epub 2006 Jul 1. PMID: 23074485; PMCID: PMC3379534.
 26. P J Foster, Ralf Buhrmann, Harry A Quigley et al. The definition and classification of glaucoma in prevalence surveys. *Br. J. Ophthalmol*.2002; 86: 238-42.
 27. Tielsch JM, Katz J, Sommer A, Quigley HA, Javitt JC. Hypertension, perfusion pressure, and primary open-angle glaucoma. The Baltimore eye study. *Arch Ophthalmol* 1995; 113(2):216–221.
 28. Leske MC, Wu SY, Hennis A, Honkanen R, Nemesure B. Risk factors for incident open-angle glaucoma: the Barbados Eye Studies. *Ophthalmology* 2008; 115: 85–93. BIBLIOGRAPHY Page 224
 29. Guedes G, Tsai JC, Loewen NA. Glaucoma and aging. *Curr Aging Sci*. 2011 Jul; 4(2):110-7. Doi: 10.2174/1874609811104020110. PMID: 21235491.
 30. Greco A, Rizzo MI, De Virgilio A, Gallo A, Fusconi M, de Vincentiis M. Emerging Concepts in Glaucoma and Review of the Literature. *Am J Med*. 2016 Sep; 129(9):1000.e7-1000.e13. doi: 10.1016/j.amjmed.2016.03.038. Epub 2016 Apr 26. PMID: 27125182.
 31. Coleman AL, Miglior S. Risk factors for glaucoma onset and progression. *Surv Ophthalmol*. 2008 Nov; 53 Suppl1:S3-10. Doi: 10.1016/j.survophthal.2008.08.006. PMID: 19038621.
 32. Wise LA, Rosenberg L, Radin RG, et al. A prospective study of diabetes, lifestyle factors, and glaucoma among African-American women. *Ann Epidemiol* 2011; 21:430–9.
 33. Girkin CA, McGwin G Jr, McNeal SF, Owsley C. Is there an association between pre-existing sleep apnoea and the development of glaucoma? *Br J Ophthalmol*. 2006 Jun; 90(6):679-81. Doi: 10.1136/bjo.2005.086082. Epub 2006 Feb 15. PMID: 16481379; PMCID: PMC1860241.
 34. Roberts TV, Hodge C, Graham SL, Burlutsky G, Mitchell P. Prevalence of nocturnal oxygen desaturation and self-reported sleep-disordered breathing in glaucoma. *J Glaucoma*. 2009 Feb; 18(2):114-8. Doi: 10.1097/IJG.0b013e318179f80c. PMID: 19225346.
 35. Khandgave TP, Puthran N, Ingole AB, Nicholson AD. The assessment of sleep apnoea as a risk factor in glaucoma. *J Clin Diagn Res*. 2013 Jul;7(7):1391- Doi: 10.7860/JCDR/2013/5383.3147. Epub 2013 Jul 1. PMID: 23998072; PMCID: PMC3749642.
 36. Lin HC, Kang JH, Jiang YD, et al. Hypothyroidism and the risk of developing open-angle glaucoma: a five-year population-based follow-up study. *Ophthalmology* 2010; 117:1960–6.
 37. Levkovitch-Verbin H, Quigley HA, Martin KR, Valenta D, Baumrind LA, Pease ME. Translimbal laser photocoagulation to the trabecular meshwork as a model of glaucoma in Rats. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci*. 2002; 43:402–10.
 38. Pradalier A, Hamard P, Sellem E, Bringer L. Migraine and glaucoma: an epidemiologic survey of French ophthalmologists. *Cephalal-*

- gia. 1998 Mar; 18(2):74-6. Doi: 10.1046/j.1468-2982.1998.1802074.x. PMID: 9533601.
39. Landers J, Goldberg I, Graham SL. Analysis of risk factors that may be associated with progression from ocular hypertension to primary open angle glaucoma. *Clin Exp Ophthalmol* 2002; 30:242-7.
40. Cursiefen C, Wisse M, Cursiefen S, Jünemann A, Martus P, Korth M. Migraine and tension headache in high-pressure and normal-pressure glaucoma. *Am J Ophthalmol*. 2000 Jan; 129(1):102-4. Doi: 10.1016/s00029394(99)00289- PMID: 10653426.
41. Mitchell P, Lee AJ, Rochtchina E, Wang JJ. Open-angle glaucoma and systemic hypertension: the Blue Mountains eye study. *J Glaucoma*. 2004 Aug; 13(4):319- 26. Doi: 10.1097/00061198-200408000-00010. PMID: 15226661.
42. Karadimas P, Bouzas EA, Topouzis F, Koutras DA, Mastorakos G. Hypothyroidism and glaucoma. A study of 100 hypothyroid patients. *Am J Ophthalmol*. 2001 Jan; 131(1):126-8. Doi: 10.1016/s0002-9394(00)00724-8. PMID: 11162988.
43. otsko SP, Jones JK. Is there an association between hypothyroidism and openangle glaucoma in an elderly population? An epidemiologic study. *Ophthalmology*. 2008 Sep; 115(9):1581-4. Doi: 10.1016/j.ophtha.2008.01.016. Epub 2008 Mar 20. PMID: 18355921.
44. Smith KD, Arthurs BP, Saheb N. An association between hypothyroidism and primary open-angle glaucoma. *Ophthalmology* 1993; 100:1580-4.
45. Boles Carenini B, Mignone U, Vadala G, et al. Glaucoma and hypothyroidism. *Acta Ophthalmol Scand Suppl* 1997; (224): 47-8.
46. Langman MJ, Lancashire RJ, Cheng KK, Stewart PM. Systemic hypertension and glaucoma: mechanisms in common and co-occurrence. *British Journal of Ophthalmology*. 2005 Aug 1; 89(8):960-3.
47. Deb AK, Kaliaperumal S, Rao VA, Sengupta S. Relationship between systemic hypertension, perfusion pressure and glaucoma: a comparative study in an adult Indian population. *Indian J Ophthalmol*. 2014 Sep;62(9):917-22
48. Vijaya L, George R, Baskaran M, Arvind H, Raju P, Ramesh SV, Kumaramanickavel G, McCarty C. Prevalence of primary open-angle glaucoma in an urban south Indian population and comparison with a rural population. The Chennai Glaucoma Study. *Ophthalmology*. 2008 Apr; 115(4):648-654.e1. doi: 10.1016/j.ophtha.2007.04.062. Epub 2007 Jul 30. PMID: 17664010.
49. Vikas Chopra et al. _Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus and the Risk of Openangle Glaucoma the Los Angeles Latino Eye Study *Ophthalmology* Volume 115, Number 2, February 2008.
50. Mitchell P, Smith W, Chey T, Healey PR. Open-angle glaucoma and diabetes: the Blue Mountains eye study, Australia. *Ophthalmology*. 1997 Apr; 104(4):712- 8. Doi: 10.1016/s0161-6420(97)30247-4. PMID: 9111268.
51. Pasquale LR, Kang JH, Manson JE, Willett WC, Rosner BA, Hankinson SE. Prospective study of type 2 diabetes mellitus and risk of primary open-angle glaucoma in women. *Ophthalmology*. 2006 Jul; 113(7):1081-6. Doi: 10.1016/j.ophtha.2006.01.066. Epub 2006 Jun 6. PMID: 16757028.
52. Klein BE, Klein R, Jensen SC. Open-angle glaucoma and older-onset diabetes. The Beaver Dam Eye Study. *Ophthalmology*. 1994 Jul; 101(7):1173-7. Doi: 10.1016/s0161-6420(94)31191-2. PMID: 8035979.
53. Ellis JD, Evans JM, Ruta DA, Baines PS, Leese G, MacDonald TM, Morris AD. Glaucoma incidence in an unselected cohort of diabetic patients: is diabetes mellitus a risk factor for glaucoma? DARTS/MEMO collaboration. Diabetes Audit and Research in Tayside Study. Medicines Monitoring Unit. *Br J Ophthalmol* 2000; 84(11):1218-1224. BIBLIOGRAPHY Page 231
54. de Voogd S, Ikram MK, Wolfs RC, Jansonius NM, Wittman JC, Hofman A, de Jong PT. Is diabetes mellitus a risk factor for openangle glaucoma? The Rotterdam Study. *Ophthalmology* 2006; 113(10): 1827-1831.
55. Vijaya L, Rashima A, Panday M, Choudhari NS, Ramesh SV, Lokapavani V, Boddupalli SD, Sunil GT, George R. Predictors for incidence of primary openangle glaucoma in a South Indian population: the Chennai eye disease incidence study. *Ophthalmology* 2014;121(7): 1370-1376
56. Casson RJ, Gupta A, Newland HS, et al. Risk factors for primary open- angle glaucoma in a Burmese population: the Meiktila Eye Study. *Clin Experiment Ophthalmol* 2007;35: 739-44
57. Ramakrishnan R, Nirmalan PK, Krishnadas R, et al. Glaucoma in a rural population of southern India: the Aravind comprehensive eye survey. *Ophthalmology* 2003; 110: 1484-90.
58. Xu L, Wang Y, Wang S, et al. High myopia and glaucoma susceptibility: the Beijing Eye Study. *Ophthalmology* 2007; 114:216-20.
59. Wong TY, Klein BE, Klein R, et al. Refractive errors, intraocular pressure, and glaucoma in a white population. *Ophthalmology* 2003; 110:211-7.
60. Perera SA, Wong TY, Tay WT, et al. Refractive error, axial dimensions, and primary open-angle glaucoma: the Singapore Malay Eye Study. *Arch Ophthalmol* 2010; 128:900-5.

61. Perera SA, Wong TY, Tay WT, et al. Refractive error, axial dimensions, and primary open-angle glaucoma: the Singapore Malay Eye Study. *Arch Ophthalmol* 2010; 128:900–5.
62. Pérez-de-Arcelus, Mónica et al. —Smoking and incidence of glaucoma: The SUN Cohort. *Medicine* vol. 96, 1 (2017): e5761. Doi:10.1097/MD.0000000000005761
63. Fan BJ, Leung YF, Wang N, Lam SC, Liu Y, Tam OS, Pang CP (2004) Genetic and environmental risk factors for primary open-angle glaucoma. *Chin Med J* 117(5):706–710
64. Renard J, Rouland J, Bron A, Sellem E, Nordmann J, Baudouin C et al (2012) Nutritional, lifestyle and environmental factors in ocular hypertension and primary open angle glaucoma: an exploratory case-control study. *Acta Ophthalmol* 91(6):505–51
65. Kang JH, Pasquale LR, Rosner BA, Willett WC, Egan KM, Faberowski N, Hankinson SE (2003) Prospective study of cigarette smoking and the risk of primary open-angle glaucoma. *Arch Ophthalmol* 121(12):1762–1768
66. Kaimbo D, Buntinx F, Missotten L (2001) Risk factors for open-angle glaucoma. *J Clin Epidemiol* 54(2):166–17
67. Wang D, Huang Y, Huang C, Wu P, Lin J, Zheng Y et al (2012) Association analysis of cigarette smoking with onset of primary open-angle glaucoma and glaucoma-related biometric parameters. *BMC Ophthalmol* 12(1):59
68. Mitchell P, Cumming RG, Mackey DA. Inhaled corticosteroids, family history, and risk of glaucoma. *Ophthalmology*. 1999 Dec; 106(12):2301-6. Doi: 10.1016/S0161-6420(99)90530-4. PMID: 10599661.
69. Garbe E, LeLorier J, Boivin JF, Suissa S. Inhaled and nasal glucocorticoids and the risks of ocular hypertension or open-angle glaucoma. *JAMA*. 1997 Mar 5; 277(9):722-7. PMID: 9042844.
70. Opatowsky I, Feldman RM, Gross R, et al. Intraocular pressure elevation associated with inhalation and nasal corticosteroids. *Ophthalmology*. 1995; 102(2):177-179.
71. Shroff S, Thomas RK, D'Souza G, Nithyanandan S. The effect of inhaled steroids on the intraocular pressure. *Digit J Ophthalmol* 2018; 24:6-9.
72. Chang LS, Lee HC, Tsai YC, Shen LS, Li CL, Liu SF, et al. Decreased incidence of glaucoma in children with asthma using inhaled corticosteroid: a cohort study. *Oncotarget* 2017; 8:105463-71.
73. Alsaadi MM, Osuagwu UL, Almubrad TM. Effects of inhaled fluticasone on intraocular pressure and central corneal thickness in asthmatic children without a family history of glaucoma. *Middle East Afr J Ophthalmol* 2012; 19:314-9.
74. Wise LA, Rosenberg L, Radin RG, et al. A prospective study of diabetes, lifestyle factors, and glaucoma among African American women. *Ann Epidemiol*. 2011;21:430e439
75. Stuart KV, Madjedi K, Luben RN, Chua SYL, Warwick AN, Chia M, Pasquale LR, Wiggs JL, Kang JH, Hysi PG, Tran JH, Foster PJ, Khawaja AP; Modifiable Risk Factors for Glaucoma Collaboration. Alcohol, Intraocular Pressure, and Open-Angle Glaucoma: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Ophthalmology*. 2022 Jun; 129(6):637-652. Doi: 10.1016/j.ophtha.2022.01.023. Epub 2022 Jan 31. PMID: 35101531; PMCID: PMC9126073.